

ACTION

StreetSpectra Pilot

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Abstract	StreetSpectra is an ACTION pilot citizen science project whose smartphone app is designed mainly for mapping the location and nature of street lights. This document describes the new overall solution of the StreetSpectra pilot, based on mobile applications, data gathering platforms, classification platforms, OpenData platforms for publishing and a geographical information system.
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StreetSpectra Pilot

1. Introduction

This document describes the evolution of the StreetSpectra project from our initial version of a single mobile app to a more comprehensive project. Over the course of 4 months we have developed an extended architecture for StreetSpectra, which gathers data through the use of a robust third-party app (Epicollect 5) and leverages existing platforms and workflows to facilitate data analysis by citizens. In this document we explain the basics of the StreetSpectra project (an ACTION pilot citizen science project). We then describe the components of the overall StreetSpectra solution and its current state of delivery. A small appendix is also included to describe AZOTEA, a mini citizen science project, born during the 3 confinement months period.

2. Motivation for the StreetSpectra project

Street lamps are a significant contributor to light pollution. However the diversity of street lamp technology means that gaining a comprehensive overview of the problem is challenging. The StreetSpectra project provides easy-to-use methods based on accessible technology to enable citizens to map and classify street light technology.

Light emitted by street lamps can be analysed using smartphone cameras, and other simple and inexpensive portable devices. We wish to turn the smartphones into scientific instruments to analyze lamps colors and their spectra¹. We will define a process and tools so that any citizen will be able to determine the kind of lamp installed on lampposts and its main characteristics. We are developing a very simple method to obtain the spectra of the lamps (StreetSpectra). This is a citizen science pilot study of the H2020-SwafS-2018-1-824603 EU project. More info about the project at <https://actionproject.eu/>

Artificial light can cause pollution that is a significant contributor to biodiversity loss and health, and also has consequences for climate change. While the current transition to LEDs can sometimes lead to energy savings, the wavelength of light emitted is more likely to produce skyglow – the atmosphere reflects light back towards the Earth’s surface - and can be much more damaging to plants and animals than old-style lights. The light that escapes to the atmosphere, due to an excess of illumination of a bad design of luminaires, is dispersed and some of this light is directed back to us. Thus,

¹ Spectra is used as a plural of spectrum.

one of the undesired effects of light pollution is the brightening of the night sky and the loss of the starry skies in our cities. The artificial illumination of our streets is one of the major contributors to light pollution.

We are experiencing a major change in the technology used for street lighting and most of the high-pressure sodium (HPS), metal halide (MH) and mercury vapor (MV) lamps are being replaced by light-emitting diode lamps (LEDs). Light pollution experts working across different fields have warned about the impact of blue artificial light at night both on human health, flora and fauna. Some of the LEDs used on the street are too white and contain a potential hazardous blue component. Read for example 'Long-Term Comparison of Attraction of Flying Insects to Streetlights after the Transition from Traditional Light Sources to Light-Emitting Diodes in Urban and Peri-Urban Settings' by Roy H. A. van Grunsven, Julia Becker, Stephanie Peter, Stefan Heller & Franz Hölker (<https://www.mdpi.com/2071-1050/11/22/6198>).

In several US cities, where the retrofit has been performed using too white LEDs, citizens are asking the authorities to re-introduce the old warm lights.

Figure 1. Image of Berlin at night taken by astronauts aboard the International Space Station (ISS) showing different illumination colors of the streets: white LEDs and orange HPS lamps. The North direction is on the right of the picture.

The replacement of street lights to LED technology is already taking place in Europe. Figure 1 shows a picture that has been taken by astronauts aboard the International

Space Station (ISS035-E-17210, taken at 2013.04.06), and shows clearly the differences in lightning between areas in Berlin where such changes have occurred. The west of the city (up in the picture) is experiencing the change from gas lights, fluorescent and mercury vapor lights to LEDs while the east of Berlin lighting is mainly composed of sodium lamps (although also is switching to LEDs) (you can browse more examples at <http://citiesatnight.org/>). There is a vast diversity of lamps used as they belong to different companies and models, ranging from very white LEDs with CCT 6000K to warm ones with 2700K and even amber lights with lower CCT.

There is scarce information on the fraction of lighting technologies employed in our cities and also of the schedule of the retrofit changes. Location, type, number of sources and light pollution brightness are needed to feed into scientific models that describe the scattering in the atmosphere and the impact of light pollution at medium and long distances from the sources.

How could the citizens participate? There are two different ways. The main one, in the *observers* role, participants take pictures using their own smartphone camera with a cheap diffraction grating and can determine and analyse the lamps' spectra. Usually all the lamps in a typical street are similar and it is not necessary to take a spectrum of every lamppost. To map the lamps getting information at both ends of the street will do. The other way to participate is to act as the *analyst* role. In this way, other citizens may just examine - from the comfort of their homes - a collection of images taken by the *observers* and submit their classification results through the Internet.

The observations & classifications archive will contain pictures with the location of the lamps) as well as their type. The contributor, or any interested citizen or researcher, can browse this open data.

The project is very well suited for educational purposes and to raise awareness of light pollution. Also, suitable [teaching materials](#) for high schools have been developed and published. The results also have scientific interest.

A comprehensive [tutorial](#) has been developed and published as part of the ACTION project that will give the citizen scientist the necessary background to involve in this project.

The designed spectrograph to record the spectra is composed by a cheap transmission grating on top of the smartphone camera. These are some of the diffraction grating suppliers. We recommend buying a diffraction grating of **500** lines/mm:

StreetSpectra Pilot

- [Edmund Optics](#)
- [Jeulin](#)
- [AliExpress](#)
- [Amazon Spain](#)
- [Amazon UK](#)
- [Amazon DE](#)

The [UCM-LICA database of street lamps spectra](#) has been updated with images of lamps spectra as seen using this simple setup.

The dedicated [StreetSpectra webpage](#) (gallery section) has some examples of spectra recorded by collaborators with their smartphones. We show in Figure 2 an striking example of the changes in street illumination (lighting retrofit) in Coslada (near Madrid) with mainly orange HPS lamps being changed to white LEDs.

Figure 2. Wide field image of the street lamps spectra obtained in Coslada (near Madrid). The lighting retrofit has changed the orange HPS lamps (2016) to mostly white LEDs.

3. StreetSpectra and the ACTION Toolkit

The ACTION toolkit is a resources collection created by the ACTION consortium. It is meant for everyone interested in using citizen science against pollution. It suits the requirements of citizen science projects, and addresses the practical problems that they face. According to the classification given in the ACTION Toolkit, StreetSpectra is an **Investigation Project**. You can find an exhaustive description of the ACTION toolkit in [The ACTION project website](#). In the Toolkit, Citizen Scientists participate in the Data Collection Step and Analyze Data Steps. In our Investigation Project, Citizen Scientists participate in Data Collection via a mobile app and data gathering platform, and in Data Analysis using a crowdsourcing platform.

Figure 3. The ACTION toolkit showing the stages of a participatory lifecycle model.

4. StreetSpectra Architecture

From the citizen scientist perspective, StreetSpectra will provide two cooperation options according to his/he/their desired role in this initiative (which are non exclusive):

- As a data collector using a mobile application (and supported by a data gathering platform invisible to him/her)
- As a data analyst using a web browser and connecting to a platform that supports data classification (crowdsourcing platform).

Finally, both citizens and researchers will have the chance of getting the classification results as datasets by pointing their web browsers to a publishing platform and also see a graphical depiction of the mapping efforts in another website (geographical information system).

It is the inclusion of the data analyst role that has made us evolve our initial architecture. As part of participating in ACTION as a pilot, we have received several inputs on how to make this possible. From the vision of a simple application that collected pictures of spectra, we have evolved into a vision that includes several components:

- **Data Gathering Platform.** This is the component that is in charge of collecting observations. It includes both a mobile application as well as a backend server.
- **Observations Database.** Part of the ACTION WP4 work is to provide pilots with an observations database.
- **Crowdsourcing Platform.** In order to increase the reliability of observations and overcome the limitations of the mobile application, we have included a platform where citizens may examine and analyse the photos and spectra taken and stored in the Data gathering Platform and submit their classifications.
- **Publication Platform.** Both observations and classifications are scientifically valuable data that should be published as Open Data and should be able to be cited as such in other papers/studies.
- **Geographical Information System (GIS).** In order to visually see the mapping efforts, a GIS platform is needed. This would allow people to coordinate in mapping their own town/city and also have coverage reports.

- **Workflow Platform.** This platform orchestrates the data flows among the above platforms, providing support for what is commonly referred to Extraction, Transformation & Loading (ETL) processes.

This overall architecture is depicted in Figure 4.

From the Citizen Scientist perspective, the entry point for StreetSpectra will be our [GUAIX Street Spectra portal](#). This portal will include information and the different links to the different platforms now being included and how to cooperate according to the role chosen.

In the remainder of this chapter we continue to describe with some detail the platforms comprising this overall solution and finally the workflows involved.

Figure 4. StreetSpectra overall solution architecture.

4.1. Data Gathering Platform: Epicollect 5

Epicollect 5 has been developed by the [Imperial College of London](#).

From their website:

Epicollect 5 is a mobile web application for free and easy data collection. It provides both the web and mobile applications for the generation of forms (questionnaires) and freely hosted project websites for data collection. Projects are created by using the web application at five.epicollect.net then downloaded to the device to perform the data collection.

We began the project using Epicollect 5 because it has a simple to use mobile application which you can tailor to your specific data collecting needs. In the case of StreetSpectra, we have streamlined the data collection tasks to allow the user to record and upload data easily (see figure 5). The main action of the Epicollect 5 mobile application is to take an image of a lamp post with the diffraction grating in front of the mobile phone main camera. We have adapted the Epicollect 5 interface so that the date and time are gathered automatically². You may upload it right now or just keep it to upload it later, using a WiFi connection to the Internet.

Figure 5. Epicollect 5 mobile application screens related to taking & keeping a picture.

On the Epicollect 5 server we created the Street Spectra Project and customized the forms for the mobile application. The interface also lists current entries from the project database (see figure 6).

² However, the user must give Epicollect 5 permission to use GPS.

Figure 6. The Epicollect 5 ACTION STREET SPECTRA project and its current entries.

However, being a very good all-purpose data gathering tool for Citizen Science projects, we found several deficiencies that made us wish to develop our own mobile application for the data gathering phase. At this point, we have engaged a subcontractor to develop a customised app which adds a number of features currently missing from Epicollect 5:

- Mapping complete streets.
The step-by-step nature of confirming metadata (i.e, position, date & time, observer's nickname) makes it a not very agile application and could drive away volunteers. It is ok for capturing an observation from time to time but mapping street lamps every few meters becomes a cumbersome process.
- Image archiving in full format.
Images are uploaded in the Epicollect 5 server in a 1024x768 low resolution format, regardless of the high resolutions found in mobile phones nowadays. This is convenient to keep the storage needs down but it is a drawback when trying to get full information of the image data.
- Annotate the region with the selected spectrum
There is no possibility to mark a region of interest in the image taken. With this feature the collaborator could indicate which of many spectra in the image is the target.
- Collaborators log.
Per user observation log is necessary to perform statistics.
- User rankings.

Note: *At the time of writing this report, there have been delays in the delivery of our custom mobile app. We continue to use Epicollect 5 as our primary mobile app & acquisition platform until the bespoke app is available.*

4.2. Observations Database

ACTION WP4 has deployed a general purpose observations database to storage observations for all pilots whose requirements exceed the simple CSV file output. This is the case for Street Spectra. We will also use it to store classifications from the Crowdsourcing platform (see section [Crowdsourcing Platform: Zooniverse](#)). It should be noted that by only using Epicollect 5 we would not need to deploy an extra observations database, since this platform stores indefinitely all observations and media (images). However, to achieve storage independence in case of our future mobile application, we have included this component in our solution. Our future mobile application will need an observations database (deployed by ACTION WP4) to store observations and media. For the time being, there is no Graphical User Interface (GUI) for this database, it can only be accessed with its [own Application Programming Interface](#) (API) The users will see the results of image classifications through Zenodo datasets.

4.3. Crowdsourcing Platform: Zooniverse

Zooniverse is a platform owned by the [Citizen Science Alliance](#).

Citizen Scientists can also be involved in the StreetSpectra project by classifying images. The tool we have chosen for this is Zooniverse. In their own words:

“The Zooniverse is the world’s largest and most popular platform for people-powered research. This research is made possible by volunteers — more than a million people around the world who come together to assist professional researchers. Our goal is to enable research that would not be possible, or practical, otherwise. Zooniverse research results in new discoveries, datasets useful to the wider research community, and [many publications](#)”.

We also considered PyBOSSA, already used in a [light pollution project](#) for classification of images taken by the International Space Station. Being a framework means more adaptability, but also more adaptation work. However, it seems that PyBOSSA is discontinued.

Zooniverse provides interested projects with two kinds of setups: private projects & public projects. In a private project, only Zooniverse registered users may collaborate. A public project is open to everybody so there is no need to register. Upon passing a revision process (which can take months) with a mentor from Zooniverse, the organization endorses and promotes the project.

Inside a project you can define one of several workflows. A Zooniverse workflow is a series of tasks to be completed in sequence. A task is a unit of work to be completed independently. There is a wide palette of tools to help the project designer in designing the task: questionnaires, forms with free texts, graphical tools to interact with images, etc. For StreetSpectra, we have settled on a very simple workflow containing one task with two tools:

- A graphical crosshair tool (see figure 7) to point the target light source. Having identified the light source, it allows disambiguation from several other light sources in the image.
- A rotating rectangle box (see figure 8) to frame the spectrum to be classified. This allows for disambiguation for the spectrum to be analyzed. It also allows further post processing by automatic tools like extracting the spectrum profile from the image. The rotating rectangle tool opens up a sub-task asking for source illumination type.

Following the recommendations of the Zooniverse team, we have settled on the following workflow parameters:

- Each image should be at least be reviewed by 5-15 users to obtain a consistent classification. We have balanced consistent classification against the number of image reviewers. In the upper bound, we would need 15x the number of CS acting as analysts than CS acting as data collectors, so we have settled on the lowest recommended figure.
- There is no “I don’t know” type of answer (see figure 8) in each image classification. This forced the user to estimate a guess. Although a simple guess may be wrong, the power of multiple analysts can give confidence in the results or at least to estimate that there is a problem in the given image.

Figure 7. Using the Light Source tool, the user first selects the light source subject to classification.

Figure 8. After the light source is identified, the user selects the Spectrum Tool to frame the spectrum corresponding to this light source. The rectangle can be conveniently rotated. When clicking to draw the rectangle, a small questionnaire pops up and the user must select his/her answer.

Figure 9. After both tools have been used and before proceeding with the next image, the user can have feedback on his classification.

SUBJECT METADATA	
id	79233090-1043-4530-9db3-4703fe0de866
url	https://five.epicollect.net/api/media/action-street-spectra?type=photo&format=entry_original&name=79233090-1043-4530-9db3-4703fe0de866_1600202318.jpg
comment	Av Cruz Roja
latitude	37.40155
longitude	-5.981935
created_at	2020-09-15T20:38:55.012Z

Figure 10. The (i) icon in each image shows additional image metadata, in this case the image identifier and URL, creation time, longitude, latitude and comment fields, all coming from Epicollect 5.

The StreetSpectra Zenodo project owner can request daily classification results via the administration web interface. As the classification results are cumulative since the beginning of the project, this process can be rather CPU heavy for a large, consolidated project. For a given image, if - let's say - 5 citizens participated in classification, we have an entry for each one of them. Thus, this file must be processed externally to obtain an aggregated classification result. This file also contains very detailed information on the context surrounding the classification (when it was made, anonymized IP, browser version, etc.)

4.4. Publishing Platform: Zenodo

Zenodo is a platform developed by the [OpenAIRE](#) project and operated by CERN.

The OpenAIRE project, in the vanguard of the open access and open data movements in Europe was commissioned by the EC to support their nascent Open Data policy by providing a catch-all repository for EC funded research. CERN, an OpenAIRE partner and pioneer in open source, open access and open data, provided this capability and Zenodo was launched in May 2013.

Following the principles stated in our Data Management Plan, we decided to make our data publicly available. The datasets being loaded into Zenodo will be the final, aggregated classification results. Although in practice this can be achieved as simply as uploading our results in [GUAIX](#), our UCM research group portal, we followed WP4

recommendation to use [Zenodo](#), an EU funded Data portal devoted to Open Data. This has provided us with two advantages:

- The datasets produced can be cited with a unique Digital Object identifier (DOI).
- It provides automatic publishing capabilities, which will be elaborated afterwards.

Figure 11. Street Spectra Zenodo community, showing some assets being uploaded.

In fact, we have already created our Street Spectra Zenodo community and have started uploading digital research objects like our tutorials and teaching materials (see figure 11). Citizen scientists will be able to obtain these datasets by pointing their browsers at Zenodo and looking for the StreetSpectra community.

4.5. Graphical Information System: Epicollect 5

Our choice for a Graphical Information System is not yet clear. Currently, there is no support for such kind of platform within ACTION WP4 and we would like to avoid deploying our own GIS, as it is a complex platform that needs expertise and maintenance outside of our research group, and For the time being, we can safely rely on Epicollect 5 server, which can display a geographical distribution of observations as they are being made (see Figure 12). However, this solution:

- is tied to the Epicollect 5 mobile application. Should we move away from it, we will lose its graphical abilities in this sense.
- doesn't show the final street map with classification results.

Figure 12. Epicollect 5 geographical distribution capabilities for StreetSpectra observations. A blob summarizes the observations and the blue area shows the observations boundaries.

4.6. Workflow Platform: Apache Airflow

Apache Airflow is open software maintained by the [Apache Source Foundation](#).

Apache Airflow is a platform created by the community to programmatically author, schedule and monitor workflows. [...]

Apache Airflow was started at Airbnb as open source from the very first commit. The community has about 500 active members who support each other in solving problems.

The various platforms presented above manage their interactions with the users independently and provide outputs, each one with its own format and idiosyncrasies. Manually coordinating its work for a given project like StreetSpectra is unfeasible. Fortunately, each one of them provides not only with interactive tools but also with an API that helps automate some tasks. And that's where Apache Airflow comes in. It provides a framework and facilities to define tasks (see figure 13) and build one of more workflows based on the execution of tasks that perform a variety of extraction, transformation and loading of data among platforms. Apache Airflow is one of the infrastructure facilities provided and deployed by ACTION WP4.

Figure 13. An example Workflow in Apache Airflow management webserver, showing tasks dependencies.

4.7. Workflows

Thanks to Apache Airflow and the existence of APIs among the platforms described above, we have been able to define two workflows (see figure 4). Note that variations from these initial designs are to be expected once implementation in Airflow begins (tools often impose their own way of doing things). The first workflow is the “data collection workflow” and the second one is the “classification workflow”.

4.7.1. Data collection workflow

In the data collection workflow (figure 4, top), the CS acting as observers, collect observations at their own pace using a mobile application (Epicollect 5 for the time being). Once a month, the task labelled as (1) will extract the monthly observations

uploaded so far, transform them into a format that the StreetSpectra database can accept and will upload them. Also, task labelled as (2) will periodically³ poll the Zooniverse platform to see if the current batch of images has been classified. If so, it will take a new batch of observations from the database and will upload them to Zooniverse.

4.7.2. Classification Workflow

In the classification workflow (figure 4, bottom), the CS, acting as analysts, examine the images, selecting a light source, its corresponding spectrum and proposed type and submit their classifications to the Zooniverse platform. Periodically⁴, a task labelled as (3) will request an export from the classifications up to date and will transform this into the classification information to be submitted to the StreetSpectra database. Task labelled as (4) will analyze incoming classifications and will write the definitive classification result for each light source. Also periodically, task (5) will form a new dataset version of classifications and will publish it at Zenodo. Also task (6) will do the same for an external GIS when we include this system (not counting Epicollect 5 acting as GIS).

5. Conclusions and Further work

From the early start of the StreetSpectra project, paused by the lockdown period in which we focused on AZOTEA, to the final deliverable, we have evolved our final vision of this CS project. The ability to introduce citizen scientists as data analyzers opens the project to more cooperation and we have developed a coherent ecosystem of data gathering, processing and analysis for StreetSpectra so indeed this can be considered a first release.

Further work in StreetSpectra includes:

- Redesign the [GUAIX StreetSpectra portal](#) to become the entry point for the new StreetSpectra pilot.
- Implement and test all the tasks and workflows. Fortunately, we have around 800 images to test with before we can promote more openly StreetSpectra.

³ Period to be defined.

⁴ Period to be defined.

- Develop Zooniverse StreetSpectra field guides. Although our D2.1 tutorial provides an in-depth introduction of classifying image spectra, a more “hands-on” approach is needed and proper help tips and field guides for data analyzers must be developed and integrated into our Zooniverse Street Spectra project.
- Localize Zooniverse StreetSpectra in Spanish, our main target for the time being. This can only happen with cooperation from the Zooniverse team and after having passed their revision process.
- Last but not least, we have further work to do in integrating our custom mobile application and media repository when it is finally delivered.

6. APPENDIX.

6.1. AZOTEA: Citizen Science during the confinement period.

AZOTEA is another “Investigation” type of Citizen Science project as described in the ACTION Toolkit (see section [StreetSpectra and the ACTION Toolkit](#)) in which the citizens were involved in the data collection.

6.1.1. Introduction and Objectives

During mid-March to the end of June 2020, we suffered a strict lockdown due to the anti-covid-19 measures. However, these exceptional circumstances opened a door to research the consequences of a decrease of human activities during this period in terms of light pollution impacts.

The idea was that citizen scientists monitored the brightness and color of the night sky using pictures taken with consumer grade cameras to evaluate variations in light pollution that may happen during the exceptional period of self-isolation. We expected a decrease of light pollution since the decrease of human activity is normally associated with darker skies. Anybody with a DSLR (digital single lens reflex) camera who is interested in the project was welcomed to participate.

The objectives were:

1. To study the impact of human activity on light pollution.
2. The evaluation of the brightness and color of the sky of our cities and towns.
3. The introduction to photometric measurement techniques with digital cameras.
4. To establish a network of digital cameras to monitor the brightness and color of the night sky.

More information in the dedicated web pages

<https://actionproject.eu/citizen-science-pilots/azotea/>

<https://guaix.ucm.es/azoteaproject>

Figure 14. Dedicated observers using an arsenal of DSLR cameras monitor the night sky brightness in Madrid.

6.1.2. From observations to scientific data

We provided instructions to the potential collaborators to install their own cameras on the roof of their homes. The first test pictures set by them were analyzed to find the best camera settings (lens, aperture, sensitivity, exposure time) according to the sky brightness of their locations. The usual observation sequence for each night is to take pictures every 6 to 12 minutes in RAW mode to preserve the linearity of the images.

The pictures are being uploaded by the collaborators to our repositories where we perform the analysis using the AZOTEA open software developed for this task. The result is a measure of the brightness of the sky in each of the four channels (R, G, G and B). The graphs for the observations of one night shows the evolution of brightness along that night. Statistics of the result for a long time allow us to determine the light pollution evolution.

Figure 15: Graphic representation of the path from observations to scientific data.

6.1.3. Project implementation

We started the task of recruiting dedicated observers as soon as possible in order not to miss nights during the confinement period in parallel with setting up the necessary infrastructure.

Figure 16: (Left) The NextCloud drive in which observers upload their images. (Right) Region of Interest where sky brightness is measured in RGB.

We set up a shared NextCloud storage server where each observer uploaded images every day. In parallel, a custom reduction pipeline tool written in Python was developed, whose task was to scan every day for new images, measure the brightness in a rectangular Region of Interest (ROI) and generate a daily CSV report.

Figure 17: (Left) Zenodo AZOTEA community where datasets are periodically uploaded. (Right) the 8 page long AZOTEA booklet.

The generated reports are accumulated in the NextCloud storage and once a month a new dataset version is compiled comprising all the accumulated observations. This dataset version is uploaded to Zenodo.

6.1.4. Calibration

We are interested in the evolution of the sky brightness (and also the color) of the night skies in the location of the observers. This evolution informs us about the variation in the light pollution both in number and intensity of the luminaries and also in the kind of luminaries. This is the same objective as the StreetSpectra project.

Our research group has recently published *"Evolution of Brightness and Color of the Night Sky in Madrid"* (2021) José Robles, Jaime Zamorano, Sergio Pascual, Alejandro Sánchez de Miguel, Jesús Gallego and Kevin J. Gaston, *Remote Sens.* 2021, 13(8), 1511; <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs13081511> where this kind of evolution is described for Madrid city using professional expensive astronomical cameras. This kind of research is now open to citizen science using the methods implemented with AZOTEA.

A relative comparison is only needed but absolute photometric calibration is desired. The calibration of the results is of extraordinary importance since we could transform to scientific units of radiance. Since the channels of the consumer grade cameras are

different from the filters used in professional astronomy we have developed a new photometric system to be used by citizens.

This research has been published in "*Synthetic RGB photometry of bright stars: definition of the standard photometric system and UCM library of spectrophotometric spectra*" (2021) [MNRAS \(2021\) https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stab997](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stab997) by Nicolás Cardiel, Jaime Zamorano, Salvador Bará, Alejandro Sánchez de Miguel, Cristina Cabello, Jesús Gallego, Lucía García, Rafael González, Jaime Izquierdo, Sergio Pascual, José Robles, Ainhoa Sánchez, Carlos Tapia.

Link to accepted paper (<https://arxiv.org/abs/2103.17009>)

With this new photometric system based on the RGB channels of the citizen cameras we can calibrate the results of the AZOTEA collaborators. A direct comparison among different places in absolute photometry is now possible.

6.1.5. Results

These are the main results we have achieved with AZOTEA:

- The AZOTEA software to process the DSLR raw images to yield night sky brightness is also available as [open software in GitHub](#).
- Monthly dataset versions are being uploaded to Zenodo (see figure 17, left)
- A “getting started” manual was also edited both in [English](#) and [Spanish](#) and uploaded to Zenodo (figure 16, right).
- The MNRAS paper mentioned above.
- A poster “AZOTEA: (Zenithal astronomy during & after the lockdown)” presenting this project has been accepted for [ALAN2021 conference](#).

Figure 18: Mockup screen from an early prototype of AZOTEA sky brightness software tool.

6.1.6. Further work

Working with DSLR images was challenging because a huge amount of raw images were generated during the lockdown period. We would like to pursue the long term objective 4 cited above of establishing a network of digital cameras monitoring the night sky. Also, we would like to open it for participation to a wider audience. For that to become feasible we need to work in two directions.

- Redesign the data reduction software from command line, batch processing mode to make it possible for each observer to execute it locally and with a

graphical user interface (see figure 18). This would solve the issue that we have in maintaining a large centralized image repository.

- Include other image taking devices other than DSLRs. For the time being, we discard mobile phones, since its processing introduces non-linearity to image brightness (gamma scaling). However, the Raspberry Pi foundation has released a [new HQ camera](#) at an affordable price. With the appropriate software we can extract raw images as they come from the sensor.
- Absolute calibration of the results using the new UCM RGB Photometric system.